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W.B YEATS'S TRANSFORMATIVE LOVE MAUD GONNE TO MOKSHA

MR. ASHOK PANDYA

Assistant Professor,
Darshan Institute of Engineering & Technology,
Gujarat

ABSTRACT

Principle object of this paper is to understand how Yeats's love transforms from Maud Gonne to moksha. It is observed that when person does not get love, he or she goes in search of ultimate and the greatest love that is GOD. When the poet, William Butler Yeats first came to contact to Maud Gonne in 1889, he was smitten by her bewitching beauty. As well as immortalising her in poetry, comparing her to Helen of Troy, he proposed to her four times but she got married to Major John MacBride in 1903. Yeats proposed to her once more, in 1916. When she refused, he proposed to her 21-year-old daughter, Iseult, who also rejected him. Chatterjee explained concept of love to Yeats in 1885. He explained that we should not ask for anything, because we will get it and get fed up with it, sooner or later. Particularly we should not ask for love. We should speak from a position of strength, not weakness, fulfilment, not emptiness, giving, not begging. Love can be obtained from giving not from begging. Life is the greatest gift of god. Yeats learnt from Indian thoughts that We are born again and again (as Yeats writes: "Grave is heaped on grave") Then His search for love started to transform from Maud Gonne to moksha (liberation from the moving world and the cycle of birth and rebirth). He understood moksha is ultimate and the greatest love.

Principle object of this paper is to understand how Yeats's love transforms from Maud Gonne to moksha. It is observed that when person does not get love, he or she goes in search of ultimate and the greatest love that is GOD. Yeats was highly influenced by Indian thoughts.

Literary and philosophical works of Sanskrit were translated into English, German and French During 18th and 19th centuries, this gave new interpretation of India among the scholars of Europe. It was Publication of Theosophical Society that inspired Yeats to look at India. Mohini Mohan Chatterji was from Theosophical Society, he was scholar of Hindu philosophy and literature. He was sent by Madame Blavatsky to European countries to teach Theosophical thoughts. He visited to Dublin at the end of 1885, Stayed for seven days. Yeats confabulated with Mohini Chatterji during his visit in Dublin. They translated the *Upanishads* together in Majorca. Despite his many connections, Yeats did not manage to visit India in his lifetime. When the poet, William Butler Yeats first came to contact to Maud Gonne in 1889, he was smitten by her bewitching beauty. as well as immortalised her in poetry, comparing her to Helen of Troy. He compares her with Helen In poem 'No second troy'

“Why, what could she have done being what she is?
Was there another Troy for her to burn?” (11-12)

"No Second Troy" was published by Yeats in 1916 in the collection *Responsibilities and Other Poems*, Helen is a mythical woman from Homer's Iliad. Alike Maud Gonne, she was considered one of the most attractive lady of her age. Helen was also somewhat responsible for opening the Trojan War that eventually inspired to the burning of the best city of Troy. When he writes poetry we can assume that he might be writing about Maud Gaunn. In 'second coming' he writes.

"Turning and turning in the widening gyre"(1)

This line has multiple meanings Ex. Yeats' idea that the life is set in a circular design of methods, and the gyre widening means it is time for the next phase the coming of Christ. It could be also for love of Maud Gaunn, His love for her might be compared with widening gyre means he is turning and turning around Maud gaun's love to win her heart. 'Falcon can not hear falconer'(2) It might be also for Maud Gaunn, She might be compared with Falcon that is not listening falconer means Yeats. She is not listening inner voice of Yeats that craving for her. It has another meaning also that now Ireland is not listening demand of England. Things fall apart; the centre cannot hold (3) When he was rejected by Maud Gaunn he might have thought that now things fall apart means his love also falls apart, and Yeats is now no able to hold love to love her. He proposed to her four times but she got married to Major John MacBride in 1903. Yeats proposed to her once more in 1916 but disappointed. His feelings of disappointment in love can be seen very well in poem *"Never Give All the Heart"*.

“Never give all the heart, for love
Will hardly seem worth thinking of
To passionate women if it seem
Certain, and they never dream..” (1-4)

It's about love of man to woman poet says one should never give all heart to women One should not love too much to anyone. Love that seems a great, it is actually lie. Poem narrates how man loved his lover and lost while she didn't respond very well. It's a sonnet, tone of poet is misery, and Yeats warns people to not love too much or should not give all your heart in love.

“Have given their hearts up to the play
And who could play it well enough” (6-7)

The word 'play' suggests that she considers love as game, so it's warning to man that women will not take love seriously. Lines 'for he gave all his heart and lost' suggest emotions of sorrow and remorse to his mistake. Love is fun for women, so never totally surrender to women in love. because Yeats felt same thing with Maud Gaunne. He loved her so much, he gave his all heart but she did not love her.

'The three Hermit' was written in 1913. In this poem he talks about what happens with soul after death. When he was writing this poem, he was in depression for disappointment in love, Maud Gonne was not ready to merry after separated from her husband. It is thought that if she had married to Yeats, his creativity of composing poetry would have died, he would have

not been able to write great poetry. She says. "You would not be happy with me. ... You make beautiful poetry out of what you call your unhappiness and you are happy in that. Marriage would be such a dull affair. Poets should never marry. The world should thank for not marrying you." (A Commentary on the Collected Poems of W.B. Yeats, 184)

People want love that can last forever. That's why they want to merry with whom they love. Yeats also wanted to merry Maud Gaunn but got disappointed. He did not lose hope after one proposal, he proposed many time. She was muse for his creative contribution. She was driving force for him. It is believed that women shape man. "If you get a good wife, you'll become happy; if you get a bad one, you'll become a philosopher." - Socrates Yeats finally wedded to Georgina Hyde Lees in 1917, while she was 25 and he was 52. They had two children. At last, his Maud obsession seemed to decrease, nearly 30 years after they first met. His love life remained a jumble.

Indian philosophy believes that happiness comes from within not from outside, inner realization is more important than outer. Gita says desire is cause of suffering. Sankrachaty's explanation about desire and moksha is stated here. Man can be free from desire by devoting inner self to god, According to sankaracharya world is illusory and god is truth (Brahm satya jagat mithya) man can be trapped in 'mohmaya' man need to learn art of detachment . "The core summary of the principles of the Gītā is that man should perform all his tasks and duties with a positive frame of mind with an attitude of detachment towards the rewards of his tasks." (EagleSpace Web) Gita says desire is cause of suffering. One should be free from desires, Yeats tried to understand this, after disappointment in love, he tried to be free from desire of love that is temporary and its influence can be seen in below lines of '*Quatrins Aphorisms*'.

"Long thou for nothing, neither sad nor gay;
Long thou for nothing, neither night nor day.
Not even 'I long to see thy longing over',
To the ever- longing and mournful spirit say." (1-4)

When man does not get love from one, he goes in search of second, frustrated lovers go to second. Human beings have something to do with love, it's not important from where they are getting. People are hungry of love. If they don't get from first, they go for second. So Yeats was also in search of second, so he proposed Maud Gaunn's daughter Iseult but she also refused. She wanted to be writer. She admired and respected Yeats very well for his literary contribution. She called herself his pupil and his guide. She knew that she was also muse for Yeats creativity. When Yeats doubted on his creativity, she was creative force behind him. Friendship was between them due to intellectual and spiritual understanding.

Yeats had love for Olivia Shakespear, who was charming, cultured and emotional lady. It was also effort to transform his love from Maud gone to Olivia Shakespear. They had sexual relationship and it was mingling of body and soul together. She was his inspiration until her death. Krishna explains one is united with this Brahman, and that salvation is in the form of becoming one with this Final Impersonal Essence. The three ways he shows are selfless action (Karma Yoga), self-transcending knowledge (Jnana Yoga), and devotion (Bhakti Yoga). Yeats tried to understand this from Indian philosophy and Bhagavad Gita and he writes his ideas regarding this in '*Quatrins Aphorisms*'.

“The ghost went by me with their lips apart
From deth’s late languor as these lines I read
On Brahma’s gateway, they within have fed
The soul upon the ashes of heart.”(1-4)

If love is too much then suffering is guaranteed. Too much is always dangerous and Yeats was victim of too much. When person begs for love at that time actually it’s not love. It is lower condition of person. Yeats was also in that condition. If anyone wants to love to anyone, one needs to maintain balance in love. Actually when people beg for love, people loose self-respect. One should never totally surrender to anyone. One should know when to let go and never compromise on self-respect. One should not lower standard for anyone or anything. Because if man is not able to love himself, he can’t love anyone. If man is not able to respect himself he can’t respect anyone.

Chatterjee explained concept of love to Yeats in 1885. He explained that we should not ask for anything, because we will get it and get fed up with it, sooner or later. Particularly we should not ask for love. We should Speak from a position of strength, not weakness, fulfilment, not emptiness, giving, not begging. Life is the greatest gift of god. Yeats learnt from Indian thoughts that we are born again and again. He writes “Grave is heaped on grave” (Mohini Chatterji 19)

His search for love started to transform from Maud Gonne to moksha (liberation from the moving world and the cycle of birth and rebirth). He understood moksha is ultimate and the greatest love. Though, He did not understand completely Indian philosophy. His disappointment of love made him realise the futility of temporary love that did not love Yeats. He was in search of salvation where he doesn’t need to beg for love and Moksha can lead him to ultimate love.

REFERENCES

1. “Bhagavad Gita principles” by Shankaracharya” ,[EagleSpace Web Team](#),22.feb.15,web.
2. M.M. Chatterji, “The Bhagwad Geeta”, Boston, 1882, P.38.print
3. Singh, Dr. Suman, “Mohini Mohan Chatterji’s Influence on W.B. Yeats”, shodh sanchayan. Web Portal of Humanity & Social Science Research.,pdf
4. Yeats, William Butler ,The Second Coming :W. B. Yeats, Pub. Shamrock Eden Publishing ,2010, p.15,print.
5. Yeats, William butler, “The Last Romantic Great Irish poets, Great Poets Series”,n.p.n.d.,p.46 print.
6. Yeats, William Butler, Selected Poems: *Great Poets Series Library of classic poets Pocket Poets*, n.p.1992, p.1234- Jeffares, Alexander Norman , “A Commentary on the Collected Poems of W.B. Yeats” n.p.n.d. , p.184.print
7. Yeats, William Butler, “Poems of William Butler Yeats” ,pub.2010.p.238, print